

A FUNCTIONAL STYLE OF LANGUAGE IS A SYSTEM OF INTERCONNECTED LANGUAGE

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Annotation. The aim of this article is to identify features of functional style as a system of interrelated language means serving a definite aim in communication.

Key words: functional style, Official, Publicistic, Scientific, Newspaper, Belles-lettres style

Functional style the coordination of the language means and stylistic devices which shapes the distinctive features of each style and not the language means or stylistic devices themselves. Each style, however, can be recognized by one or more leading features which are especially conspicuous. For instance the use of special terminology is a lexical characteristic of the style of scientific prose, and one by which it can easily be recognized.

A style of language can be defined as a system of coordinated, interrelated and inter-coordinated language means intended to full-fill a specific function of communication and aiming at a defined effect. Style of language is a historical category.

The English literary system has evolved a number of styles easily distinguishable one from another. They are not homogeneous and fall into several variants of having some central point of resemblance or better to say. They are:

- 1) Official (documents and papers);
- 2) Scientific (brochures, articles, other scientific publications);
- 3) Publicistic (essay, public speech);
- 4) Newspaper style (mass media);
- 5) Belles-lettres (genre of creative writing);

Each of mentioned here styles can be expressed in two forms: written and oral.

Stylistics is a science that examines the complex of stylistically marked elements of any language level.

1) scientific style is employed in professional communication to convey some information. Its most conspicuous feature is the abundance of terms denoting objects, phenomena and processes characteristic of some particular field of science and technique. Also precision clarity logical cohesion.

2) Official style is the most conservative one. It uses syntactical constructions and archaic words. Emotiveness is banned out of this style.

3) Publicistic style is famous for its explicit pragmatic function of persuasion directed at influencing the reader in accordance with the argumentation of the author.

4) Newspaper style – special graphical means are used to attract the readers attention.

5) Belles-lettres style – the richest register of communication besides its own language means, other styles can be used besides informative and persuasive functions, belles-lettres style has a unique task to impress the reader aesthetically.

A functional style is thus to be regarded as the product of a certain concrete task set by the sender of the message. Functional styles appear mainly in the literary standard of a language. The literary standard of the English language, like that of any other developed language, is not homogeneous as it may seem. In fact the standard English literary language in the course of its development has fallen into several subsystems each other of which has acquired its own

peculiarities which are typical of the given functional style. The members of the language community, especially those who are sufficiently trained and responsive to language variations, recognize these styles as independent wholes. The peculiar choice of language means is primarily predetermined by the aim of the communication with the result that a more or less closed system is built up. One set of language media stands in opposition to other sets of language media with other aims, and these other sets have other choices and arrangements of language means. What we here call functional styles are also called registers or discourses. In the English literary standard we distinguish the following major functional styles: 1) The language of belles-lettres. 2) The language of publicistic literature. 3) The language of newspapers. 4) The language of scientific prose. 5) The language of official documents.

As has already been mentioned, functional styles are the product of the development of the written variety of language. Each FS may be characterized by a number of distinctive features, leading or subordinate, constant or changing, obligatory or optional. Most of the FSs, however, are perceived as independent wholes due to a peculiar combination and interrelation of features common to all with the leading ones of each FS. Each FS is subdivided into a number of substyles. These represent varieties of the abstract invariant. Each variety has basic features common to all the varieties of the given FS and peculiar features typical of this variety alone. Still a substyle can, in some cases, deviate so far from the invariant that in its extreme it may even break away. We clearly perceive the following substyles of the five FSs given above. The belles-lettres FS has the following substyles: a) The language style of poetry; b) The language style of emotive prose; c) The language style of drama. The publicistic FS comprises the following substyles: a) The language style of oratory; b) The language style of essays; c) The language style of feature articles in newspaper and journals. The newspaper FS falls into: a) The language style of brief news items and communiqués; b) The language style of newspaper headings and c) The language style of notices and advertisement. The scientific prose FS also has three divisions: a) The language style of humanitarian sciences; b) The language style of "exact" sciences; c) The language style of popular scientific prose. The official document FS can be divided into four varieties: a) The language style of diplomatic documents; b) The language style of business documents; c) The language style of legal documents; d) The language style of military documents. The classification presented here is by no means arbitrary. It is the result of long and minute observations of factual material in which not only peculiarities of language usage were taken into account but also extralinguistic data, in particular the purport of the communication. However, we admit that, this classification is not proof against criticism. Other schemes may possibly be elaborated and highlighted by different approaches to the problem of functional styles. The classification of FSs is not bound to reflect more than one angle of vision. Thus, for example, some stylistic consider that newspaper articles should be classed under the functional style of newspaper language, not under the language of publicistic literature. Others insist on including the language of everyday-life discourse into the system of functional styles.

References:

1. Essays on Style and Language, ed. by Fowler R Ldn, 1967. -P. 32

2. Galperin I. R. “Перевод и стилистика.”— В сб.: Теория и методика учебного перевода. 1960. -Р. 45
3. Galperin I. R. – “О понятиях «стиль» и «стилистика”. «Вопросы языкознания», 1973. -Р. 210
4. Galperin I. R. – “Информативность единиц языка.” М., 1974.
5. Гальперин И.Р. English Stylistics. Учебник./И.Р."LIBROCOM". 2010.-336 с
6. Кузнец М.Д., Скребнев Ю.М. Стилистика английского языка. - Л.: Государственное учебнопедагогическое издательство, 1960. – 172 Р

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